

William E. Winkler, Record Linkage, and the Statistical Capacity of the Federal Statistical System

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Abstract

William E. Winkler (1946 – 2022) spent the majority of his career at the U.S. Census Bureau. At Census Bill made fundamental contributions to record linkage, file edit-imputation, data quality metrics, and disclosure limitation, among other areas. The Jaro-Winkler distance, a string comparator metric, is well-regarded in computer science and many other fields. In large-scale applications, he pioneered the use of advanced methods of indexing and sorting huge files. He combined technical expertise in probability, statistics, algorithms, machine learning, and programming with a deep understanding and appreciation of applied problems, such as record linkage for decennial undercount estimation. Currently, his research gate site lists 111 publications with more than 41,000 reads and over 4,900 citations; his google scholar site lists 55 publications with over 8,200 citations. Bill was a prolific presenter at conferences and advisor to national statistical agencies around the world. Still, he enjoyed working closely with individuals and helping them with their challenges. He was a mentor and supporter of colleagues both inside and outside of Census. Beyond contributing to work on specific problems, Bill advocated for enhancing the statistical and analytical capacity of the Federal Statistical System at all levels. As a systems thinker, he clearly saw that combining the necessary skills, resources, environment, leadership, and incentives could enable a team to make substantial improvement in data collection and processing, statistical methods, and production of statistical products and reports.

Key Words: Approximate string matching; Data linkage; Data matching; Deduplication; Disclosure limitation; Edit-Imputation; Entity resolution; File matching; Fuzzy matching; Identity resolution; Probabilistic linkage; String comparison metric; String distance metric

1. Overview

The purpose of this proceedings paper is to summarize my presentation from the invited paper memorial session “In Memory of Bill Winkler” at the Joint Statistical Meetings, Monday, August 7, 2023. The comments include personal notes and are not intended as a comprehensive review of the many contributions and accomplishments of William E. Winkler, or Bill as he preferred to be called. It is the opinion of the author that technical work completed by Bill Winkler will be valuable for many generations of students, researchers, and analysts in official statistics. In addition, his interest in helping people and his thoughtful consideration of what is needed for success in large-scale statistical operations are notable and worthy of remembrance.

The statements in this paper are the responsibility of the author and not of other individuals or organizations.

The proceedings paper first describes when the author met Bill Winkler. It then comments on a few of his many statistical and other contributions. The paper discusses Bill's interests in protecting public software, helping others, and enhancing the statistical capacity of national statistics systems. The paper concludes with thanks and a small selection of references.

2. Meeting Bill Winkler

In the late Fall of 1991, or perhaps in the early Spring of 1992, I was in my first year of graduate school in Statistics at Harvard University. Professor Donald Rubin was my Ph.D. advisor. One day Dale Rinkel, a long-serving senior administrative assistant in the department, told me in her office that Don wanted to see me in the statistics library on the 6th floor of Harvard's Science Center. I was a little worried because this was out of the ordinary. Approaching the library, I could see through the glass that Don was talking to someone. They seemed to be talking amicably, so my apprehension at being called to a meeting decreased a little. Entering the library, Don introduced me to Bill Winkler. He then told me I would be working for Bill in the summer of 1992 at the U.S. Census Bureau in Washington, D.C. That started my interaction with Bill Winkler. It was a pleasure knowing him as a mentor, colleague, and friend for over 30 years.

After the introduction, Bill and I sat in the library and talked about record linkage, statistical models, programming, and logistics of working at the Census (actually in Suitland, Maryland) for a couple of hours. The goal of the summer was to investigate the use of logistic regression, latent class models, and extensions in census record linkage operations. After the 1980 decennial census, in preparation for the 1990 decennial census, test censuses and post enumeration surveys (PES) were conducted in several sites across the United States. In each of these areas, the two lists of the population, the census and the PES, were compared to determine who was present in both enumerations and who was "captured" in one but not the other. Record linkage is the process using available information to determine whether individuals have had information recorded in two or more files. The process is challenging when the files are large, there are no unique identification numbers (the decennial census does not collect Social Security or any other such unique number), and there can be errors or ambiguities in the data. There is a history of applied practice, computing and statistical methods, and statistical theory concerning record linkage. Bill was interested in innovations in many aspects of record linkage and Census operations more generally. Areas of interest included statistics, probability, algorithms, computer science, and technology.

Back in the early 1990s, the test and evaluation datasets for record linkage contained just over 100,000 pairs of records (after blocking on key characteristics of records). One reason for this limitation is that clerical review (human comparison of entries in data files) was performed to determine the true link status of pairs of records, one from each enumeration in an area. Clerical review is time consuming and typically expensive. The other limitations were related to computing processing speed, computer memory storage size, and efficiency of algorithms. Applications today involve files that are several orders of magnitude larger. Gains in this capacity were achieved partly due to advances in technology. Improvements in algorithms for sorting, indexing, and otherwise processing data, to which Bill contributed significantly, also were important. One concern Bill raised about very large applications was that it becomes very challenging to verify that record linkage operations are producing accurate results overall and in subgroups of the population. He saw the difficulty in conducting honest and rigorous evaluation. Yet such work at verifying quality is essential.

Insights from Bill ultimately lead to work in my Ph.D. dissertation (e.g., Larsen and Rubin 2001). One fascinating insight (to me) was that statistical criteria for estimation do not always correspond to effective applications. The goal in record linkage is to find matching pairs and exclude nonmatching pairs. Statistical models that fit the data (seemingly) well are not necessarily so useful for record linkage. Maximum likelihood estimation is agnostic concerning record linkage goals. Bayesian methods that take advantage of record linkage experience have been considered as a possible improvement. Bill examined using three instead of two classes in latent class models applied to record linkage pairs, mixture models with interactions amongst variables instead of latent class models, restrictions on probabilities, and adjustments for partial agreements on string variables as ways to improve models for record linkage performance. Having a truth deck (the clerically reviewed data) was essential for comparing models and methods in terms of actual record linkage performance. One can think of asking similar questions about data mining,

clustering, and data visualization. What problem do these methods really solve? How can results be rigorously evaluated in terms of the ultimate goals and decisions? The interplay between fitting data well and solving real world problems is a rich area for future work.

3. Many Technical Contributions

Bill Winkler made several contributions that are useful and important in a variety of large-scale applications. His primary areas of research and development included

- Record linkage,
- Edit/Imputation,
- String Comparator metrics/distances,
- Estimation of latent class models with constraints, and
- Indexing and sorting of very large files.

He studied, followed, and utilized advances in several areas, including

- Statistics,
- Computer Science,
- Operations Research, and
- Probability.

Today, the list of areas surely would include Data Science.

Bill shared his contributions widely. He presented at national and international conferences and gave talks and seminars at national statistical agencies around the world. He authored many proceedings papers and Census research reports. He coauthored a book (Herzog, Scheuren, and Winkler 2007), book chapters (e.g., Winkler 1995, 2009, 2021), and peer reviewed papers (e.g., Winkler 1990, 2004, 2014; Scheuren and Winkler 1993, 1997).

It is beyond the scope of this memorial session proceedings paper to go into depth on research areas. Public reference sites, including Bill's own Research Gate and Google Scholar webpages, more fully list his publications. As he had multiple publications in several areas, his publications usually reference additional examples of his work.

4. Helping Others and Protecting Public Software

I was not the first, nor the last, graduate student in Statistics to benefit from involvement and time spent at the U.S. Census Bureau in the Statistics Research Division (SRD), the Center for Statistical Research and Methodology (CSRМ), and other areas. A real, important problem with statistical and computing challenges can be a great early-career motivator. Access to data and mentors who take an active interest are fabulous.

Besides us graduate students, Bill provided training to individuals and teams at Census. It is said that Bill was always open to talking to people about their statistical problems and helping work toward solutions. Outside of Census, Bill gave seminars and advised national statistical agencies and academic centers. Indeed, he did not view his role as limited to developing methods in his office, which of course he did in abundance, but disseminating his work and knowledge broadly.

One prime example of a product developed at Census with Bill's leadership is the Census matching program Rec Link, now Big Match. This program for large-scale record linkage was developed over 2-3 decades by Bill and several colleagues including Matthew Jaro, Thomas Belin,

Yves Thibaudeau, Ned Porter, Bill LaPlant, Bill Yancey, and probably others whom I do not know. It is beyond the scope of this paper to list all the research papers and reports related to this huge undertaking. The program was a Census production-scale program. That means its algorithms and computing are fast enough and professionally developed for use in full-scale U.S. Census operations. For example, it can be used to perform record linkage of a decennial census (330 million records) to the primary Social Security Administration file (1 billion records). Originally written in Cobol, it was ported to C with some use of Fortran along the way.

The record linkage programs, as well as other programs for data quality evaluation and improvement, were shared internally with groups at Census. Bill with collaborators provided training in use of the programs as well as in record linkage theory and methods. The programs were shared outside of Census with some researchers and national statistical agencies and offices.

It is my understanding that Bill personally considered requests for the software and was careful concerning its distribution. Bill advocated for software created at Census to remain in the public domain and be a public good. He was concerned that companies (some very large) would take developments and ideas, patent them, and then restrict access to the programs and methods. An interest in society and science over possible profits is a noble cause that not all are willing or able to undertake. Given his technical knowledge and expertise, it is noteworthy that he thought it important to undertake this stewardship role.

5. Programming and Statistical Capacity of National Statistical Systems

A number of Bill's publications address (directly and indirectly) the fact that a statistical operation has numerous facets, and all can be critical. These include but are not limited to

- Preprocessing of data files and data cleaning,
- Checks on performance at various stages of a complex operation, and
- Evaluating outcomes of processes and results for reasonable and accuracy.

Not all steps are covered by traditional mathematical statistics theory. Bill's approach to large scale problems was consistent with modern ideas of exploring data and understanding multidimensional complexities of problems. Some references that discuss data quality and the overall statistical production process, connecting multiple steps and dimensions, include Herzog, Scheuren, and Winkler (2007) and Winkler (2004, 2006, 2009, 2014, and 2021).

One particular research report that emphasized the human and team element in the context of large-scale statistical problem solving was Winkler and Hidioglou (1998). An organization needs people who understand Theory, Required analyses, and Programming. Approaching a major challenge, a deficit in one area can lead to inefficiency or irrelevance. The article discusses the idea that an analyst-programmer can be quite valuable for a statistical organization. Examples of an analyst-programmer include a methodologist (economist, demographer, statistician, or other) who can program and a programmer/informatician who understands theory and methods. In most cases, a team of personnel will be required to bring these skills together.

The goals of the endeavors of an analyst-programmer team are envisioned to encompass the research and development of new methods, the creation of a prototype set of software, demonstration of the potential of new approaches, and delivering an improved production system. The article asks questions, including

- "Why is one group able to perform successfully and another not?"
- "How can a statistical organization create a group that can move good ideas into practice?"

Winkler and Hidioglou (1998) give examples of the advantages of having an analyst-programmer team engaged on a project. Statisticians who can program can more easily study new methods. If programs meet statistical needs, then statisticians can do more. A programmer who understands the method of analysis can produce better and more accurate code. The programmer might check the accuracy of the code by conducting analyses and statistical evaluations.

Research software sometimes is understood by a small group doing research. It could serve as a prototype for production software, but it might not be developed with that purpose in mind. Production software by contrast has several requirements. These include

- Improvements in speed and size of application,
- Compatibility of programming languages with existing systems,
- User interfaces,
- Control information for production processing,
- Documentation,
- Production and reporting of variables of interest and tables for output,
- Support (development and ongoing improvements and adaptations) for the software, and
- Statistical diagnostics and checks.

In the authors' view, successful operations expand the skills and knowledge of team members. They remove isolation between analysts, researchers, and programmers: "isolation can be counterproductive". In this context, the authors describe the advantage of generalized statistical systems that can be adapted to multiple applications. A general system that can be used in more than one context has a greater potential than a one-use system for sharing expertise and developments across groups and agencies. Generalized systems have the potential to "raise institutional skill level".

A number of elements are required for the analyst-programmer model to be effective. The list of elements in Winkler and Hidioglou (1998) includes

- Good management and leadership,
- Priority for the project,
- Individuals with knowledge, experience, and/or ability to develop,
- Computing hardware,
- Computing software,
- Sufficient time and resources, and
- Support/interest of the user community.

Together the comments and suggestions in this research report advocate for a statistical organization or national statistical office to be organized around building capacity, committed to investing in personnel development, and proactive in preparing for the future.

6. Concluding Comments

Bill Winkler was a friend to many and helpful to many more. He was an intellectual leader in record linkage, edit/imputation, and several other areas. He maintained international connections and had a broad impact. He was thoughtful as a leader at Census and in the profession. He provided training and opportunities for his colleagues, advocated and worked for software as a public good, and saw the value of investing in the programming/analysis/production capacity of the federal statistical system. I was fortunate to have been introduced to him at Harvard during my first year of graduate school in Statistics and to have known him for many years.

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